

Fig. S1. Alignments of RNA-seq reads to the *M.persicae* nAChR beta 1 gene sequence, identifying clones 5 and 67 as possessing homozygous/heterozygous R81T mutations respectively, while 4106A, 37 and 5191A show as wild type at this loci.

Fig. S2. Gene ontology term enrichment of: A) genes upregulated in resistant clones and B) downregulated in resistant clones.

Fig. S3. qPCR confirmation of induced overexpression of *M. persicae* P450 genes in the F1 versus parental generations of *D. melanogaster* after experimental crossings. Bar graphs show mean fold-change and SEM of genes of interest relative to housekeeping genes. Asterisk's indicate significant differences in expression (*p = < 0.05, **p = < 0.01, ***p = < 0.001, ****p = < 0.0001).

Fig. S4. Phylogenetic analysis of P450s experimentally validated to metabolise flupyradifurone or neonicotinoid insecticides. *M. persicae* CYP6CY3 and CYP6CY4 are highlighted in purple. UPGMA consensus tree created using Geneious Prime software. P450s shown are: **A.gos** (*Aphis gossypii*) CYP6CY14 (MT268675.1), **M.per** (*Myzus persicae*) CYP6CY3 (KF218350.1), CYP6CY4 (NP_001352549.1), **B.tab** (*Bemisia tabaci*) CYP6CM1v4 (Acc. no. WFG82911.1), CYP6CX4 (Acc. no. OR232201.1), CYP6EM1(OP762532.1), **D.mel** (*Drosophila melanogaster*) CYP6G1 (NP_001286335.1), **N.lug** (*Nilaparvata lugens*) CYP6ER1vA (AUT13961.1), **A.mel** (*Apis mellifera*) CYP6AQ1(NP_001191991.1), CYP9Q2 (XP_392000), CYP9Q3 (XP_006562363), **A.vag** (*Andrena vaga*) CYP9FT2 (GBLF01017912.1), **C.cun** (*Colletes cunicularius*) CYP9FZ2(GBUJ01004521.1), **D.nov** (*Dufourea novaeangliae*) CYP9DL4 (XP_015439019.1), **E.mex** (*Eufriesea mexicana*) CYP9Q8 (XP_017758640.1), **H.lab** (*Habropoda laboriosa*) CYP9Q9 (XP_017794730.1), **M.qua** (*Melipona quadrifasciata*) CYP9Q10 (KOX69484.1), **M.ful** (*Macropis fulvipes*) CYP9FU2 (GBNX01015534.1), **M.hae** (*Melitta haemorrhoidalis*) CYP9FU3 (GBVK01019397.1).